

PCHF POSTGRADUATE COURSE
IN HEART FAILURE
LONDON

2nd Edition

A NOVEL COURSE IN HEART FAILURE MANAGEMENT

February 2021 to October 2022

Royal Brompton & Harefield
NHS Foundation Trust

Venue: The Royal Society of Medicine,
1 Wimpole Street, Marylebone, London, UK

Endorsed by
British Society for Heart Failure
British Cardiovascular Society

Based on the curriculum of the ESC Heart Failure Association (HFA)

COURSE ORGANISATION

Institutions

Royal Brompton and Harefield Hospital Trust, London
London Institute of Medical Science
British Society for Heart Failure
British Cardiovascular Society

Course Directors

Thomas F. Lüscher, MD, FRPC, FESC, London, United Kingdom
Martin Cowie, MD, FRPC, FESC, London, United Kingdom
Kim Fox, MD, FRCP, FESC, London, United Kingdom
Richard Grocott-Mason, MD, FRCP, London, United Kingdom
Shouvik Halder, MD, FACC, London, United Kingdom
Paul Kalra, MD, MRCP, FRCP, Portsmouth, United Kingdom
Milton Packer, MD, FACC, Dallas, United States

Course Organisation

Ruth Amstein, PhD, FESC
Christine Lohmann

Advisory Board

A renowned international advisory board will guarantee for a high-quality education integrating the curriculum of the British Society for Heart Failure and the ESC Heart Failure Association. It consists of the following members:

Jeroen J. Bax, MD, FESC, FACC, Leiden, Netherlands
Michael Böhm, MD, FESC, Homburg/Saar, Germany
John A. Camm, MD, FRCP, FESC, FACC, London, United Kingdom
John Cleland, MD, FRCP, FESC, FACC, Glasgow, United Kingdom
Gerhard Hindricks, MD, FESC, Leipzig, Germany
John McMurray, MD, FRCP, FESC, FACC, FAHA, Glasgow, United Kingdom
Bertram Pitt, MD, Ann Arbor, MI, United States
Dirk van Veldhuisen, MD, FESC, FACC, Groningen, Netherlands

Representatives of the major sponsors (without vote)

INVITATION

Dear Colleagues,

Heart failure is the end-stage of most forms of heart disease such as hypertension, coronary artery disease and acute myocardial infarction, congenital heart disease, cardiomyopathies and consequently a major cause of morbidity and mortality. This development needs to be appropriately addressed by novel training programmes for medical doctors to develop a professional profile, competent in all aspects of care for patients with acute and/or chronic heart failure.

The London Postgraduate Course in Heart Failure Management (PCHF) is a two-year programme consisting of 6 modules, each module with a 3.5-day duration. The course includes a total of 160 hours of classroom time and 140 hours of self-study, and its successful completion leads to a **Certificate in Heart Failure Management**. Unlike at congresses, the PCHF modules offer interactive sessions between speakers and participants, workshops, rapid fire sessions, live case seminars and ward visits. The course covers all relevant aspects of heart failure such as diagnostic procedures, imaging, pharmacotherapy, devices and mechanical circulatory support systems. The course structure with its hands-on approach enables participants both to improve their clinical skills in diagnostic procedures and increase their therapeutic knowledge.

Considering the broad spectrum of the course, PCHF is clearly one of the most exciting educational experiences in cardiology available today, and it is made possible thanks to a strategic collaboration among academia, professional organisations and industry partners. After highly constructive and encouraging feedbacks from the PCHF courses in Zurich and the present London PCHF course we are delighted to announce a new edition in London in 2021/22.

We look forward to receiving your application and meeting you in London.

With best regards,

Thomas F. Lüscher
MD, FRPC, FESC

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MD, FRCP, FESC

Paul Kalra
MD, MRCP, FRCP

Richard Grocott-Mason
MD, FRCP

Martin Cowie
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Shouvik Halder
MD, FACC

COURSE CONTENT & DATES

YEAR 1 MAIN TOPICS 2021

Module 1 10 -13 February 2021

How to Approach Heart Failure

Epidemiology of heart failure: incidence and prevalence, risk factors.
How to assess HF: clinical signs and symptoms, use of biomarkers, ECG and exercise tests. Comorbidities. Theoretical and practical application of different imaging modalities: Echo, CMR, CT and nuclear techniques.
Pathophysiology of HF: interpretation of haemodynamic parameters, pump dysfunction. Management of HF in congenital heart disease.

Module 2 23-26 June 2021

Different Forms of Heart Failure

HF encompasses HFpEF, HFmrEF and HFrfEF according to the classification of the ESC guidelines. Focus on HFpEF, diagnostic procedures and treatments. Comorbidities linked to HFpEF, including dyspnoea, sleep disturbances, depression, obesity, diabetes, hypertension, iron deficiency, atrial fibrillation, gender aspects.
Different forms of cardiomyopathies, diagnostic techniques and treatments, cardiac amyloidosis. Practical imaging sessions with patient cases in Echo, CMR, CT and Nuclear/PET.

Module 3 13-16 October 2021

Treatment and Follow-up of Heart Failure

This module focuses on HF with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF) and its pathophysiology. Role of the renin angiotensin system, the sympathetic nervous system and related treatment targets: ACE-inhibitors, AT2-antagonists, ARNIs, betablockers, I_f-channel blockers, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, diuretics and digitalis. Pathophysiology of renal injury and the cardiorenal syndrome.
Arrhythmias in HF, including atrial fibrillation and ventricular tachycardias, guidelines and indications for cardiac resynchronisation therapy (CRT).
How to read and interpret randomised controlled trials, device trials and registry-based trials in HF. The patient journey in HF.

YEAR 2 MAIN TOPICS 2022

Module 4 19–22 January 2022

Catheter Ablation and Devices in Heart Failure

Catheter ablation of atrial fibrillation and ventricular tachycardias with live case transmissions or live in-a-box. Tips and tricks for catheter ablation with selected case reports and expert review lectures. Practical training for ICD and CRT implantation in a simulation lab, virtual reality cases from the EP lab, role of wearables and implantable monitors in HF and practical echo optimisation. How to build a successful career, how to become a leader and key rules for scientific publishing.

Module 5 22–25 June 2022

Multidisciplinary Procedures

Emphasis is placed on valve disease in the context of HF: anatomy and imaging of the aortic, mitral and tricuspid valve. Decision making and patient selection for valve interventions. Role of the heart team. Assessment and management of aortic stenosis and functional mitral regurgitation. Live in-a-box demonstrations and ultrasound-guided valvular intervention. Revascularisation strategies in ischemic cardiomyopathy, management of cardiogenic shock including indications for ECMO. Cardio-oncology and cardiotoxic drugs in cancer treatment. Regenerative medicine in HF and stem cell therapy, myocarditis and takotsubo. How to build up a HF clinic.

Module 6 12–15 October 2022

Acute and Advanced Heart Failure

Definition and epidemiology of acute HF, triggers and mechanisms. Classification of acute HF. Prehospital and early management strategies, clinical evaluation and investigation, diagnostic tools and risk markers. Therapies of acute HF including oxygen, ventilatory support, inotropes and vasopressors. Definition of advanced HF including dyspnoea, fluid retention, cardiac dysfunction, impairment of functional capacity. Short-term and long-term mechanical circulatory support. Heart transplantation: indications and timing, immunosuppressive drugs, complications after transplantation. Palliative care.

GENERAL INFORMATION

Course Dates

YEAR 2021
10-13 February, 23–26 June, 13–16 October
YEAR 2022
19–22 January, 22–25 June, 12–15 October

Course Venues

The Royal Society of Medicine, 1 Wimpole Street, Marylebone, London, UK
Royal Brompton & Harefield Hospitals

Course Language

The course will be held in English.

Exams

Each of the modules will be followed by a multiple-choice examination. An examination can be repeated once if the performance is unsatisfactory. The examinations of at least 5 modules will have to be passed successfully to be eligible for certification.

Course Structure

The London Postgraduate Course in Heart Failure Management (PCHF) is a 2-year course consisting of 6 modules, each module with a 3.5-day duration. The course includes a total of 160 hours of classroom time and 140 hours of self-study, and its successful completion leads to a Certificate in Heart Failure Management.

Organisation and Project Management

Zurich Heart House
Ruth Amstein, PhD, FESC
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CH-8032 Zurich, Switzerland
Phone: +41 44 250 40 87
E-mail: ruth.amstein@zhz.ch

FEES & APPLICATION

Course Fee

The course fee is GBP 3000. Travel and accommodation costs are not included and will have to be paid on an individual basis.

Application Procedure

The candidates will be selected by members of the selection committee based on their interest in heart failure as documented in their motivation letter, rotations in a heart failure unit and /or publications in this field. Furthermore, career options in heart failure management, as foreseen by their supervisor, will be taken into consideration. Candidates at the end of their training or junior staff members will have priority among the applicants.

Applicants are asked to submit the following documents in English:

- Curriculum vitae
- List of publications
- Grades of medical school
- Motivation letter
- Recommendation letter of supervisor
- Outline of future career

For additional information regarding the application process, please visit our website: www.heartfailurecourse.uk

February 2021 to
October 2022
(6 modules, 3.5 days per module)
Please submit your application
ONLINE by October 31, 2020 to:
www.heartfailurecourse.uk

AUSPICES AND STRATEGIC PARTNERS

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Harefield Hospital Trust, London
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NHS Foundation Trust

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